

**The 03rd International Conference on
University-Industry Collaborations
for Sustainable Development
(ICSD 2026)**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Editors

Prof. Ranjith Dissanayake | Dr. Pradeep Gajanayake

IN VITRO PHARMACOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF *Leucas zeylanica*

M.M.S.T.C.M. Kulathunga*, K.D.M. Manthila, H.K. Diwyanjalee, W.A.A. Shavindi,
M.N.F. Sifaniya, H. Madushika, D.N.A.W. Samarakoon

Department of Biomedical Science, Faculty of Health Science, KIU, Sri Lanka.

*Correspondence E-mail: shehanikulathunga3@gmail.com, TP: +94701257375

Abstract: The genus *Leucas* is a member of the Lamiaceae family. The *Leucas* species, especially the plant of *Leucas zeylanica*, is a commonly used medicinal plant in Ayurvedha, Siddha, and Unani for treating various body inflammations, diabetic patients, oxidative stress, parasitic infections, and various body infections. On such background, this review aims to highlight the pharmacological potential of *Leucas zeylanica*. The literature review was conducted using Google Scholar, PubMed, and Hinari. We explored the database using “Pharmacological potential of *Leucas Zeylanica* in vitro assays.” The initial 361 articles were narrowed down to 48 after careful filtering based on the topic and abstract, following the PRISMA flowchart. The *Leucas zeylanica* methanol extracts have higher antioxidant activity, due to the presence of high phenolic and flavonoid content. Significant anti-inflammatory effects were seen through the inhibition of nitric oxide, TNF- α , IL-6, COX-2, and iNOS, with diterpenoids identified as a major component. The aqueous extracts of *Leucas zeylanica* demonstrated a significant reduction in blood glucose levels and inhibited α -amylase, α -glucosidase, and advanced glycation end-products. The *Leucas zeylanica* aqueous and methanol extracts showed dose-dependent anthelmintic activity comparable to albendazole-like medicines. The *Leucas zeylanica* toxicity assessments conducted using zebrafish embryo assays reported low cytotoxicity and good safety margins. Phytochemical analyses confirmed the support of a lot of bioactive compounds towards observed pharmacological effects. The *Leucas zeylanica* methanol extracts had stronger in vitro antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and anthelmintic qualities than aqueous extracts. The presence of various bioactive compounds in *Leucas zeylanica* supports traditional use and highlights its potential for the development of plant-based therapeutics.

Keywords: Anthelmintic; Antidiabetic; Anti-inflammatory; Antioxidant Activity; *Leucas zeylanica*

Partner Universities

University of Peradeniya
Sri Lanka

University of Ruhuna
Sri Lanka

Chiang Mai University
Thailand

Rajarata University of
Sri Lanka

Horizon Campus
Sri Lanka

Naresuan University
Thailand

University of Sri Jayawardenepura
Sri Lanka

RMIT University
Australia

University of Sabaragamuwa
Sri Lanka

Vilnius Gediminas Technical University
Lithuania

Mid Sweden University
Sweden

Tallinn University of Technology
Estonia

University of Huddersfield
England

KDK College of Engineering, Nagpur
India

In Collaboration with

Technical Partners

